

ω_1										
ω_2										
ω_3										
\vdots				\ddots						
ω_p										
\vdots						\ddots				
ω_h										
\vdots								\ddots		
ω_{k-1}										
ω_k										
\vdots										
ω_{n-1}										
ω_n										

Prevalence of Common Words in Randomly Generated Languages

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Given a language L , how many languages, among all the possible ones, have at least one word in common with L ?

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1 Abstract

I provide here a set of formulas for the study of the prevalence of languages with common words (same sound and same meaning) if we assume a completely random generation of the languages themselves. In particular, given a language L , how many languages, among all the possible ones, have at least one word in common with L ? And considering a subset of all the possible languages, what is the probability that this subset includes at least one language with at least one word in common with L ? The probability of finding a given disyllabic word in different languages merely by chance is about $1/10$ when we consider 7000 languages. The probability of finding at least one language with at least one disyllabic word in common with a given language is about 97% when we consider 40 languages. The equations derived in this document can be used to compute these kinds of probabilities in function of the number of syllables and of the number of languages considered: by comparing them with experimental results it is possible to highlight similarities between languages that are not merely due to chance.

2 Introduction

The association of a phonological word ω and a meaning m gives rise to the word $w = (\omega, m)$. We indicate $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_n\}$ the set of all the possible phonological words while we say that $M = \{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k\}$ is the set of all the possible meanings. The set M is assumed to be the same for each language. Then we define the generic language as

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad L = \{(\omega_1, m_1), (\omega_2, m_2), \dots, (\omega_k, m_k)\}$$

The words of L are shaded grey in Table 1. We can generate all the possible languages by moving up and down the cells shaded grey with the only restriction that there must always be no more than one grey cell for each row.

	m_1	m_2	m_3	...	m_p	...	m_h	...	m_{k-1}	m_k
ω_1										
ω_2										
ω_3										
\vdots				\ddots						
ω_p										
\vdots						\ddots				
ω_h										
\vdots								\ddots		
ω_{k-1}										
ω_k										
\vdots										
ω_{n-1}										
ω_n										

Table 1. By moving up or down the k grey cells of this table according to the rule that there must be no more than one grey cell for each row, we can generate each one of all the possible languages of k words.

That said, the number of possible sets of k phonological words is given by the number of combinations of k elements extracted from Ω : $C_{n,k} = \binom{n}{k}$. Each one of these sets generates $k!$ languages, by permutation of the meanings. Therefore, the number of all the possible languages that can be generated by Ω, M is

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad \lambda = \binom{n}{k} k!$$

We are interested in calculating how many of these λ languages contain at least one word in common with a given language L .

3 Languages with at least one word in common with L

If we introduce the event E_i given by “*the meaning m_i is associated with the phonologic word ω_i* ”, then the probability that a randomly generated language has at least one word in common with L is given by $P(\cup_{i=1}^k E_i)$ and by applying PROP. 1 we can write

$$P(\cup_{i=1}^k E_i) = \sum_{h=1}^k (-1)^{h-1} S_h$$

with $S_h = \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_h \leq k} (P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap E_{i_h}))$. In our case we have

$$P(E_i) = \frac{1}{n}, \quad P(E_i \cap E_j) = \frac{1}{n(n-1)}, \quad P(E_i \cap E_j \cap E_k) = \frac{1}{n(n-1)(n-2)}, \dots$$

Then we can write

$$S_h = \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_h \leq k} \frac{1}{n(n-1) \dots (n-h+1)} = \binom{k}{h} \frac{1}{n(n-1) \dots (n-h+1)} = \binom{k}{h} \frac{(n-h)!}{n!}$$

n	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55
k	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
λ	5040	32760	116280	303600	657720	1256640	2193360	3575880	5527200	8185320
λ''_1	685	4665	14945	34525	66405	113585	179065	265845	376925	515305
λ_1	1707	7847	21487	45627	83267	137407	211047	307187	428827	578967
	1707	7847	21487	45627	83267	137407	211047	307187	428827	578967
λ'_1	2211	9431	24751	51171	91691	149311	227031	327851	454771	610791
$\frac{\lambda''_1 + \lambda'_1}{2}$	1448	7048	19848	42848	79048	131448	203048	296848	415848	563048

Table 2. Values λ, λ_1 for some values of n, k . The number λ_1 has been calculated by both direct inspections of all the possible languages and by the use of Eq. 4. The value of λ'_1 comes from Eq. 23. The number λ''_1 has been calculated by using Eq. 15. The arithmetical mean between λ'_1, λ''_1 is also indicated, to show how it approximates the exact value λ .

Then, the conclusion is

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad P(\cup_{i=1}^k E_i) = \sum_{h=1}^k (-1)^{h-1} \binom{k}{h} \frac{(n-h)!}{n!}$$

This probability can also be expressed as λ_1/λ , therefore we conclude that the number of languages with at least one word in common with L is given by

$$\text{Eq. 4} \quad \lambda_1 = \lambda P(\cup_{i=1}^k E_i) = \sum_{h=1}^k (-1)^{h-1} \binom{k}{h} \frac{(n-h)!}{(n-k)!}$$

In Table 1 you can see the value of λ_1 for $k = 4$ and n from 10 to 55. These values have been calculated by both direct inspections of all the possible randomly generated languages and by the use of Eq. 4 (this is why you have identical values on two rows). Values λ'_1 and λ''_1 will be discussed in the following paragraphs. The table has been generated by the following script.

3.1 Script

This code calculates λ_1 by direct inspection of all the possible randomly generated languages of $k = 4$ words and $n = 10, 15, \dots, 55$ possible phonological words. It also performs the same calculation by Eq. 4. It calculates λ'_1 by Eq. 15, and λ''_1 by Eq. 23.

```

-----
% file name = at_least_one_word_new_formula_mean_count
% date of creation = 9/02/2022
%-----
% This script calculates the number of languages with at least one word in common
% with L by direct inspection, by a minoration, by a majorization, by the mean between
% minoration and majoration
%-----
close all
clear all
n_array = [10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55]
siz = size(n_array);
num = siz(2);
k = 4
for s=1:num
    n = n_array(s)
    lambda(s) = bincoeff(n,k)*factorial(k);
    %-----
    % calculation of the minoration of lambda_1
    %-----
    for h = 1:k
        addends(h) = bincoeff(n-k,k-h)*bincoeff(k,h)*factorial(k-h);
    endfor
    % calculation of lambda_1
    lambda_1 = 0;
    for h = 1:k
        lambda_1 = lambda_1 + addends(h);
    endfor
    lambda_1_min(s) = int64(lambda_1)
    %-----
    % calculation of the exact value of lambda_1
    %-----
    kf = factorial(k);
    % the array that contains all the possible combinations of k significant
    array = nchoosek(1:n,k);
    temp = size(array);
    lines = temp(1);
    % for each combination we build all the possible permutations and among them
    % we search for the ones with at least one word in common with L
    count(1:lines,1:kf) = 0;

```

```

for i=1:lines
array_temp = perms(array(i,:));
for j = 1:kf
for p = 1:k
if (array_temp(j,p) == p)
count(i,j) = 1;
endif
endfor
endfor
endfor
lambda_1 = 0;
for i = 1:lines
for j = 1:kf
lambda_1 = lambda_1 + count(i,j);
endfor
endfor
lambda_1_count(s) = int64(lambda_1)
%-----
% calculation of the majoration of lambda_1
%-----
% function for sum of  $((-1)^i)/i!$ 
function summation = sum (h,p)
if (h-p < 7)
summation = 0;
for i = 0:h-p
summation = summation +  $((-1)^i)/\text{factorial}(i)$ ;
endfor
else
summation = 1/e;
endif
endfunction
% calculation of the addends of the double summation (in h and p)
for h = 1:k
mu = min(h,k-h);
for p = 0:mu
addends(h,p+1) = bincoeff(n-k,k-h)*bincoeff(k,h)*factorial(k-h)*bincoeff(k-h,p)*...
bincoeff(h,p)*factorial(h-p)*factorial(p)*factorial(p)*sum(h,p);
endfor
endfor
% calculation of the double summation (in h and p)
double_sum = 0;
for h = 1:k
mu = min(h,k-h);
for p = 0:mu
double_sum = double_sum + addends(h,p+1);
endfor
endfor
% calculation of lambda_1
first_term = factorial(k)*(bincoeff(n,k)-bincoeff(n-k,k));
lambda_1 = first_term - double_sum;
lambda_1_maj(s) = int64(lambda_1)
% calculation of the mean of lambda_1_min and lambda_1_maj
lambda_1_mean(s) = (lambda_1_maj(s) + lambda_1_min(s))/2

```

```

%-----
% calculation of lambda_1 with the exact formula
%-----
for h = 1:k
    addends(h) = ((-1)^(h-1))*bincoeff(k,h)*factorial(n-h)/factorial(n);
endfor
% calculation of lambda_1
lambda_1 = 0;
for h = 1:k
    lambda_1 = lambda_1 + addends(h);
endfor
lambda_1_exact(s) = int64(lambda(s)*lambda_1)
endfor
% saving arrays as files
save ('L_1_count','lambda_1_count')
save ('L_1_maj','lambda_1_maj')
save ('L_1_min','lambda_1_min')
save ('L_1_mean','lambda_1_mean')
save ('L_1_exact','lambda_1_exact')
save ('L_exact','lambda')
save ('array_n','n_array')
-----

```

4 Probability of at least one language with a least one word in common with L

The probability of finding at least one language with at least one word in common with L among a number l of randomly generated languages can be calculated by considering a binomial distribution of l attempts with a probability of success given by λ_1/λ . Such a distribution is given by

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad p(i) = \binom{l}{i} \left(\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda}\right)^i \left(1 - \frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda}\right)^{l-i}$$

Then the probability of having at least one success is

$$P = \sum_{i=1}^l p(i) = \sum_{i=0}^l p(i) - p(0) = 1 - \binom{l}{0} \left(\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda}\right)^0 \left(1 - \frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda}\right)^l \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad P = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda}\right)^l$$

If we consider languages built on a collection of 25 sounds, five vowels, and 20 consonants, we have 25 syllables of type CV and 25 of type VC. By adding further 50 syllables of three or more sounds, we have a total of 250 syllables. The total number of disyllabic phonetic words is then $n = 250^2 = 62500$. If we assume that each language uses only $k = 5000$ disyllabic words, then the number of possible languages is given by

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad \lambda = \binom{62500}{5000} 5000! \sim 10^{23890}$$

By substituting n, k in Eq. 4 and by employing Wolfram Alpha we also find

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad \lambda_1 = \sim 10^{23889}$$

If we now assume $l = 7000$, we find

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad P = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{10}\right)^{l=7000} \sim 1$$

The calculation for trisyllabic words would require $n = 250^3, k = 10000$ and it exceeds the computational time at my disposal with Wolfram Alpha. The solid line in Figure 1 shows that considering only 60 languages, we are already sure to find one with at least one word in common with L , and with 20 languages this probability is almost 90%.

Figure 1. The probability of having at least one language with at least one disyllabic word in common with L in function of the number of languages considered (horizontal axis), in other words, it is the plot of Eq. 9 in function of l .

5 Probability of finding a given word

Another problem of interest might be: given a word $\bar{w} = (\bar{\omega}, \bar{m})$ what is the probability of finding it at least once by searching l languages? The number of possible languages containing \bar{w} is given by

$$\text{Eq. 10} \quad \lambda_{\bar{w}} = \binom{n-1}{k-1} (k-1)!$$

Then, the probability of selecting such a language among the λ possible languages is

$$\frac{\lambda_{\bar{w}}}{\lambda} = \frac{\binom{n-1}{k-1} (k-1)!}{\binom{n}{k} k!} = \frac{(n-1)!}{(k-1)! (n-k)!} \frac{k! (n-k)! (k-1)!}{n! k!} = \frac{k-1}{n k} = \frac{1}{n}$$

This means that if I try with l languages the probability that I fail in finding one of the $\lambda_{\bar{w}}$ languages is

$$\left(1 - \frac{\lambda_{\bar{w}}}{\lambda}\right)^l = \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^l$$

and the probability of succeeding at least once is

Eq. 11
$$P(l) = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{\lambda_{\bar{w}}}{\lambda}\right)^l = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^l$$

In the case of disyllabic words, we have $P(l = 7000) = 0.1060$, which is the probability that a given disyllabic word $\bar{w} = (\bar{\omega}, \bar{m})$ is present in one of the 7000 human languages by chance only (see also Figure 2).

Figure 2. The probability of finding a given word $\bar{w} = (\bar{\omega}, \bar{m})$ in at least one of l languages, for $l \in [1,100]$ (Eq. 11).

6 Conclusions

The probability of finding a given disyllabic word in different languages merely by chance is about 1/10 when we consider 7000 languages. The probability of finding at least one language with at least one disyllabic word in common with a given language is about 97% when we consider 40 languages. The equations derived in this document can be used to compute these kinds of probabilities in function of the number of syllables and of the number of languages considered and to compare them with experimental results to highlights similarities between languages not merely due to chance.

7 Useless approximated values

In the next three paragraphs, I derive a lower and an upper approximation for λ_1 . The arithmetical mean of these two values seems to closely follow the exact value of λ_1 , but the upper approximation has an expression that is more complex than the exact expression λ_1 , so these analyses are of very little interest to the reader.

7.1 Languages with h words in common with L

How many are the possible sets of Ω with h phonological words included in L ? We can select the common phonological words in $C_{k,h}$ different ways, while the remaining $k - h$ words can be selected in $C_{n-k,k-h}$ different ways. Hence, the number is

$$\text{Eq. 12} \quad N_h = \binom{n-k}{k-h} \binom{k}{h}$$

From each of the elements of these sets, we can generate $k!$ languages by permutation of the meanings. Therefore, the number of languages that have h phonological words in common with L is

$$\text{Eq. 13} \quad \lambda_{\geq 0}^{(h)} = N_h k! = \binom{n-k}{k-h} \binom{k}{h} k!$$

Among these languages, the number of those in which the h phonological words in common with L have also the same meaning they are associated to in L is given by

$$\text{Eq. 14} \quad \lambda_h^{(h)} = N_h (k-h)! = \binom{n-k}{k-h} \binom{k}{h} (k-h)!$$

We can then also state that

$$\text{Eq. 15} \quad \lambda_1 \geq \sum_{h=1}^k \binom{n-k}{k-h} \binom{k}{h} (k-h)!$$

7.2 Languages with at least h words in common with L

The difference between $\lambda_{\geq 0}^{(h)}$ and $\lambda_0^{(h)}$ (number of languages with h phonological words in common with L but no words in common with L) gives the number of languages with h phonological words in common with L and at least one word in common with L . To calculate $\lambda_0^{(h)}$, let us consider one of the $\lambda_h^{(h)}$ languages with h words in common with L (see table below¹). If we permute the h meanings of the words in common so that no one remains associated with its original phonological word, we obtain some of the languages we are searching for.

m_1	m_2	m_3	...	m_h	m_{h+1}	...	m_{k-1}	m_k
ω_1	ω_2	ω_3	...	ω_h	ω_{h+1}	...	ω_{k-1}	ω_k

¹ In this table, we have arranged the order of the elements such that the first h words are those in common with L .

This permutation can be performed in

$$\text{Eq. 16} \quad v(h) = h! \sum_{i=2}^h \frac{(-1)^i}{i!}$$

different ways, as explained in par. 8. Hence, we can say that

$$\text{Eq. 17} \quad \lambda_0^{(h)} \geq \lambda_h^{(h)} v(h) = \binom{n-k}{k-h} \binom{k}{h} (k-h)! h! \sum_{i=2}^h \frac{(-1)^i}{i!}$$

It can also be observed that if we operate a substitution between an element ω_i , $i > h$, and an element ω_j , $j \leq h$, and we then permute the remaining $h-1$ common meanings, such that no one remains associated with its original phonological word, we obtain other elements of $\lambda_0^{(h)}$. Now, since the element ω_i can be selected in $k-h$ different ways and the element ω_j can be selected in h different ways, and given also that the permutations are in this case $v(h-1)$, we have

$$\text{Eq. 18} \quad \lambda_0^{(h)} \geq \lambda_h^{(h)} (v(h) + h(k-1)v(h-1))$$

This same algorithm can be followed for a number $p \leq \min(h, n-h)$ of elements, but in this case, the number of possible substitutions is $C_{k-h,p} C_{h,p}$ and the number of permutations is $v(h-p)$. The conclusion is then

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_0^{(h)} \geq \lambda_h^{(h)} & \left(\binom{k-h}{0} \binom{h}{0} v(h) + \binom{k-h}{1} \binom{h}{1} v(h-1) + \binom{k-h}{2} \binom{h}{2} v(h-2) + \dots \right. \\ & \left. \dots + \binom{k-h}{\min\{h, k-h\}} \binom{h}{\min\{h, k-h\}} v(h - \min\{h, k-h\}) \right) \Rightarrow \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Eq. 19} \quad \lambda_0^{(h)} \geq \lambda_h^{(h)} \sum_{p=0}^{\min\{h, k-h\}} \binom{k-h}{p} \binom{h}{p} v(h-p)$$

We can conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Eq. 20} \quad \lambda_{\geq 1}^{(h)} & \leq \lambda_{\geq 0}^{(h)} - \lambda_0^{(h)} = N_h \left(k! - (k-h)! \sum_{p=0}^{\min\{h, k-h\}} \binom{k-h}{p} \binom{h}{p} v(h-p) \right) = \\ & = \binom{n-k}{k-h} \binom{k}{h} k! \left(1 - \frac{(k-h)!}{k!} \sum_{p=0}^{\min\{h, k-h\}} \left(\binom{k-h}{p} \binom{h}{p} (h-p)! \sum_{i=0}^{h-p} \frac{(-1)^i}{i!} \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

7.3 Languages with at least one word in common with L

The number of languages with at least one word in common with L is then given by

$$\text{Eq. 21} \quad \lambda_1 = \sum_{h=1}^k \lambda_{\geq 1}^{(h)} \leq$$

$$\leq k! \sum_{h=1}^k \binom{n-k}{k-h} \binom{k}{h} \left(1 - \frac{(k-h)!}{k!} \sum_{p=0}^{\mu} \left(\binom{k-h}{p} \binom{h}{p} (h-p)! \sum_{i=0}^{h-p} \frac{(-1)^i}{i!} \right) \right)$$

where we made the position

$$\text{Eq. 22} \quad \mu = \min\{h, k-h\}$$

By using Eq. 31 we can also write

$$\text{Eq. 23} \quad \lambda_1 \leq$$

$$\leq k! \left(\binom{n}{k} - \binom{n-k}{k} - \sum_{h=1}^k \binom{n-k}{k-h} \binom{k}{h} \frac{(k-h)!}{k!} \sum_{p=0}^{\mu} \left(\binom{k-h}{p} \binom{h}{p} (h-p)! \sum_{i=0}^{h-p} \frac{(-1)^i}{i!} \right) \right)$$

8 Further mathematical notes

PROP. 1 (probability of the union of n events). Given the events E_1, E_2, \dots, E_n , the probability of their union is given by

$$\text{Eq. 24} \quad P(\cup_{i=1}^n (E_i)) = S_1 - S_2 + S_3 + \dots + (-1)^{n-1} S_n$$

where

$$S_1 = \sum_{i=1}^n (P(E_i)), \quad S_2 = \sum_{i_1 < i_2 \leq n} (P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2})), \quad S_3 = \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < i_3 \leq n} (P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap E_{i_3})),$$

$$\dots, \quad S_n = \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_n \leq n} (P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap E_{i_n})) = P(E_1 \cap E_2 \cap \dots \cap E_n)$$

Proof. Let us consider only the two events E_1, E_2 . If we define the events $E'_1 = E_1 - (E_1 \cap E_2)$ and $E'_2 = E_2 - (E_1 \cap E_2)$ we can write

$$E_1 \cup E_2 = E'_1 \cup E'_2 \cup (E_1 \cap E_2)$$

The events $E'_1, E'_2, (E_1 \cap E_2)$ have no elements in common, therefore we can write

$$P(E_1 \cup E_2) = P(E'_1 \cup E'_2 \cup (E_1 \cap E_2)) = P(E'_1) + P(E'_2) + P(E_1 \cap E_2)$$

On the other hand, we also have

$$P(E_1) = P(E'_1 \cup (E_1 \cap E_2)) = P(E'_1) + P(E_1 \cap E_2) \Leftrightarrow P(E'_1) = P(E_1) - P(E_1 \cap E_2)$$

$$P(E_2) = P(E_2' \cup (E_1 \cap E_2)) = P(E_2') + P(E_1 \cap E_2) \Leftrightarrow P(E_2') = P(E_2) - P(E_1 \cap E_2)$$

By substituting the expression just found for $P(E_1'), P(E_2')$ in the expression previously found for $P(E_1 \cup E_2)$, we have

$$\text{Eq. 25} \quad P(E_1 \cup E_2) = P(E_1) + P(E_2) - P(E_1 \cap E_2)$$

which is the thesis for two events. The general formula can be proved by induction (but I warn you that it is a long and boring undertaking). Let us assume that it is true for n events, then we can apply Eq. 25 and write

$$\text{Eq. 26} \quad P\left(\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n (E_i)\right) \cup E_{(n+1)}\right) = P\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n (E_i)\right) + P(E_{(n+1)}) - P\left(\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n (E_i)\right) \cap E_{(n+1)}\right)$$

On the other hand, we also have

$$\begin{aligned} P\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n (E_i)\right) + P(E_{(n+1)}) &= S_1 + P(E_{(n+1)}) - S_2 + S_3 + \dots + (-1)^{n-1} S_n = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n (P(E_i)) + P(E_{(n+1)}) - S_2 + S_3 + \dots + (-1)^{n-1} S_n = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} (P(E_i)) - S_2 + S_3 + \dots + (-1)^{n-1} S_n \end{aligned}$$

Then, Eq. 26 can be written

$$\text{Eq. 27} \quad P\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{n+1} (E_i)\right) = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} (P(E_i)) - S_2 + S_3 + \dots + (-1)^{n-1} S_n - P\left(\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n (E_i)\right) \cap E_{(n+1)}\right)$$

We also know that

$$\text{Eq. 28} \quad P\left(\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n (E_i)\right) \cap E_{(n+1)}\right) = P\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n (E_i \cap E_{(n+1)})\right)$$

By applying the thesis (assumed true for n) to Eq. 28 we have

$$\begin{aligned} &P\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n (E_i \cap E_{(n+1)})\right) = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n (P(E_i \cap E_{(n+1)})) - \sum_{i_1 < i_2 \leq n} \left(P\left(\left(E_{i_1} \cap E_{(n+1)}\right) \cap \left(E_{i_2} \cap E_{(n+1)}\right)\right)\right) + \\ &+ \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < i_3 \leq n} \left(P\left(\left(E_{i_1} \cap E_{(n+1)}\right) \cap \left(E_{i_2} \cap E_{(n+1)}\right) \cap \left(E_{i_3} \cap E_{(n+1)}\right)\right)\right) + \dots + \end{aligned}$$

$$+(-1)^{n-1} \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_n \leq n} \left(P \left((E_{i_1} \cap E_{(n+1)}) \cap (E_{i_2} \cap E_{(n+1)}) \cap \dots \cap (E_{i_n} \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right) \right)$$

This expression can be simplified in the following one

$$\begin{aligned} P \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n (E_i \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right) &= \sum_{i=1}^n \left(P(E_i \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right) - \sum_{i_1 < i_2 \leq n} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right) + \\ &+ \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < i_3 \leq n} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap E_{i_3} \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right) + \\ &+ \dots + (-1)^{n-1} \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_n \leq n} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right) \end{aligned}$$

If we now put this expression in Eq. 27, we have

$$\text{Eq. 29} \quad P \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{n+1} (E_i) \right) = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} (P(E_i)) - S_2 - \sum_{i=1}^n \left(P(E_i \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right) + S_3 +$$

$$\sum_{i_1 < i_2 \leq n} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right) + \dots +$$

$$+(-1)^{n-1} S_n - (-1)^{n-2} \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_{n-1} \leq n} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap E_{i_{n-1}} \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right) -$$

$$-(-1)^{n-1} \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_n \leq n} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right)$$

Note now that

$$\begin{aligned} S_2 + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(P(E_i \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right) &= \\ = \sum_{i_1 < i_2 \leq n} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2}) \right) + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(P(E_i \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right) &= \sum_{i_1 < i_2 \leq n+1} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2}) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$S_3 + \sum_{i_1 < i_2 \leq n} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right) = \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < i_3 \leq n+1} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap E_{i_3}) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (-1)^{n-1} S_n - (-1)^{n-2} \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_{n-1} \leq n} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap E_{i_{n-1}} \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right) = \\
& = (-1)^{n-1} \sum_{\substack{i_n=1 \\ i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_n \leq n}} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap E_{i_n}) \right) + \\
& + (-1)^{n-1} \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_{n-1} \leq n} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap E_{i_{n-1}} \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right) = \\
& = (-1)^{n-1} \sum_{\substack{i_n=1 \\ i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_n \leq n+1}} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap E_{i_{n+1}}) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

By substituting these expressions in Eq. 29, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
P\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{n+1} (E_i)\right) &= \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} (P(E_i)) - \sum_{i_1 < i_2 \leq n+1} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2}) \right) + \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < i_3 \leq n+1} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap E_{i_3}) \right) + \\
& + \dots + (-1)^{n-1} \sum_{\substack{i_n=1 \\ i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_n \leq n+1}} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap E_{i_{n+1}}) \right) - \\
& - (-1)^{n-1} \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_n \leq n} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

We can also observe that

$$\sum_{i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_n \leq n} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right) = \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_n \leq n+1} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap E_{(n+1)}) \right)$$

Moreover, $(-1)^{n-1} = -(-1)^n$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
P\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{n+1} (E_i)\right) &= \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} (P(E_i)) - \sum_{i_1 < i_2 \leq n+1} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2}) \right) + \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < i_3 \leq n+1} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap E_{i_3}) \right) + \\
& + \dots + (-1)^{n-1} \sum_{\substack{i_n=1 \\ i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_n \leq n+1}} \left(P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap E_{i_{n+1}}) \right) +
\end{aligned}$$

$$+(-1)^n \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_n \leq n+1} (P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap \dots \cap E_{(n+1)}))$$

But this is the thesis for $n + 1$ events. Then, if the thesis is true for two events, if assuming it true for n events means that it is true for $n + 1$ events, the must conclude that it is true for any number of events by the principle of induction ■

PROP. 2 (Vandermonde's identity). It is true that:

$$\text{Eq. 30} \quad \sum_{i=0}^k \binom{m}{k-i} \binom{n}{i} = \binom{m+n}{k}$$

Proof. The simplest way to prove this identity is probably by using a figure like the one below. In how many ways can we build the set K by using i elements of N (which includes n elements) and $k - i$ elements of M (which includes m elements)? We can select the i elements of N in $C_{n,i}$ in different ways, and the $k - i$ elements of M in $C_{m,k-i}$ ways. Then the answer is $C_{n,i}C_{m,k-i}$. If we then assume that it goes from zero (we pick up only elements from M) to k (we select only elements from N), then we have that the number of possible sets K is

$$\sum_{i=0}^k \binom{m}{k-i} \binom{n}{i}$$

But this number is also the number of ways to build the set K from the $m + n$ elements of $M \cup N$ and this number is given by $C_{m+n,k} = \binom{m+n}{k}$ and this proves the thesis ■

Figure 3. This Venn diagram suggests a simple proof for Vandermonde's identity.

For us it is also useful to write Vandermonde's identity as follows:

$$\text{Eq. 31} \quad \sum_{h=1}^k \binom{n-k}{k-h} \binom{k}{h} = \binom{n}{k} - \binom{n-k}{k}$$

PROP. 3 (No one at its place). Let us consider the first n integer numbers, each one associated with the position indicated by its value (1 is associated with the first position, 2 with the second, and so forth). The number of permutations of these n numbers such that none of them is associated with the position indicated by its value is given by

Eq. 32
$$v(n) = n! \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{(-1)^k}{k!}$$

Proof. If we indicate E_i the event “number i is placed in position i -th” we can write

$$P(E_i) = \frac{1}{n}, \quad P(E_i \cap E_j) = \frac{1}{n(n-1)}, \quad P(E_i \cap E_j \cap E_k) = \frac{1}{n(n-1)(n-2)}, \quad \dots$$

On the other hand, if we consider the event “at least one number occupies the position indicated by its value” (event E), according to PROP. 1 we can write

$$E = \bigcup_{k=1}^n E_k \Rightarrow P(E) = S_1 - S_2 + S_3 + \dots + (-1)^{n-1} S_n$$

where

$$S_1 = \sum_{i=1}^n (P(E_i)) = \frac{n}{n} = 1$$

$$S_2 = \sum_{i_1 < i_2 \leq n} (P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2})) = \frac{C_{n,2}}{n(n-1)} = \frac{1}{n(n-1)} \frac{n!}{2!(n-2)!} = \frac{n!}{2!n!} = \frac{1}{2!}$$

$$S_3 = \sum_{i_1 < i_2 < i_3 \leq n} (P(E_{i_1} \cap E_{i_2} \cap E_{i_3})) = \frac{C_{n,3}}{n(n-1)(n-3)} = \frac{1}{n(n-1)(n-3)} \frac{n!}{3!(n-3)!} = \frac{1}{3!}$$

...

$$S_n = P(E_1 \cap E_2 \cap \dots \cap E_n) = \frac{1}{n!}$$

So we have proved so far that

$$P(E) = 1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3!} - \frac{1}{4!} + \dots + \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n!}$$

It follows that if we consider the event E^c (“none of the numbers occupies its position”), we find

$$P(E^c) = 1 - P(E) = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{3!} + \frac{1}{4!} - \dots + \frac{(-1)^n}{n!} = \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{(-1)^k}{k!}$$

And considering that $P(E^c) = v(n)/n!$, we find Eq. 32 ■

8.1 Script

The following code written in Octave verifies Eq. 32 by direct count of the permutations in which none of the first integers occupies its place (the place indicated by its value). This script calculates the values collected in Table 2 and plots Figure 4.

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
$\nu(n)$	0	1	2	9	44	265	1854	14833	133496	1334961
	0	1	2	9	44	265	1854	14833	133496	1334961
$n!/e$	0.37	0.73	2.21	8.83	44.15	264.87	1854.1	14832.9	133496.1	1334960.9
$P(E^c)$	0	0.50	0.333	0.3750	0.3667	0.3681	0.3679	0.3679	0.3679	0.3679

Table 3. First row: the value of $\nu(n)$ obtained by direct count of the permutations. Second row: the same value calculated as $n! \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{(-1)^k}{k!}$. Third row: the approximation $n!/e$. Fourth row: $P(E^c) = \nu(n)/n!$

Figure 4. On the left: plots of $\nu(n) = n! \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{(-1)^k}{k!}$ and of $\frac{n!}{e}$. On the right: plots of $P(E^c)$ (black) and of its limit $\frac{1}{e}$ (red).

```

% file name = nessuno_al_suo_posto
% date of creation = 2/02/2022
clear all
close all
n_max = 10
%-----
% we calculate the number of permutations of the first n integers such that none
% of the numbers is the number of its position by direct inspection of the permutations
%-----
for n=1:n_max
    array = [1:1:n];
    permutations = perms(array);
    temp = size(permutations)
    lines = temp(1,1)
    for i=1:lines
        counter(i) = 0;
        for j=1:n
            if ( permutations(i,j) != j)
                counter(i) = counter(i) + 1;
            endif
        endfor
        if ( counter(i) == n)

```

```

    counter(i) = 1;
else
    counter(i) = 0;
endif
endfor
sum(n) = 0;
for i=1:lines
    sum(n) = sum(n) + counter(i);
endfor
endfor
%-----
% we calculate the same number by a formula
%-----
for n =1:n_max
    sum2(n) = 0;
    for k=2:n
        sum2(n) = sum2(n) + ( (-1)^k/factorial(k) );
    endfor
    probability(n) = sum2(n)
    sum2(n) = factorial(n)*sum2(n);
    sum3(n) = factorial(n)*( 1 + (1/e) );
endfor
probability2 = ( 1 + (1/e) )
%-----
% plotting
%-----
figure(1)
plot([3:n_max],sum(3:n_max),'-k','Linewidth', 1)
hold on
plot([3:n_max],sum2(3:n_max),'--k','Linewidth', 1)
hold on
plot([3:n_max],sum3(3:n_max),':k','Linewidth', 1)
xlabel('n','fontsize',15);
ylabel('number of permutations','fontsize',15);
legend('direct inspection','formula','aproximation','location','NORTHWEST','fontsize',15)
grid minor
figure(2)
plot([3:n_max],probability(3:n_max),'-k','Linewidth', 1)
hold on
plot([3:n_max],[probability2:probability2],'-k','Linewidth', 1)
xlabel('n','fontsize',15);
ylabel('probability','fontsize',15);
grid minor

```

9 List of the symbols and their meanings

λ	$\binom{n}{k} k!$	Number of languages of k words
N_h	$\binom{n-k}{k-h} \binom{k}{h}$	Number of sets of phonological words with h phonological words in common with L
$\lambda_{\geq 0}^{(h)}$	$N_h k! = \binom{n-k}{k-h} \binom{k}{h} k!$	Number of languages with h phonological words in common with L
$\lambda_h^{(h)}$	$N_h (k-h)! = \binom{n-k}{k-h} \binom{k}{h} (k-h)!$	Number of languages with h words in common with L
$\lambda_0^{(h)}$	$\lambda_h^{(h)} \sum_{p=0}^{\mu} \left(\binom{k-h}{p} \binom{h}{p} v(h-p) \right)$	Number of languages with h phonological words in common with L and zero words in common with L
$\lambda_{\geq 1}^{(h)}$	$\lambda_{\geq 0}^{(h)} - \lambda_0^{(h)} =$ $= N_h \left(k! - (k-h)! \sum_{p=0}^{\mu} \binom{k-h}{p} \binom{h}{p} v(h-p) \right)$	Number of languages with h phonological words in common with L and at least one word in common with L
λ_1	$\lambda_1 = \sum_{h=1}^k \lambda_{\geq 1}^{(h)} =$ $= k! \sum_{h=1}^k N_h \left(1 - \frac{(k-h)!}{k!} \sum_{p=0}^{\mu} \binom{k-h}{p} \binom{h}{p} v(h-p) \right)$	Number of languages with at least one word in common with L
$v(h)$	$h! \sum_{i=2}^h \frac{(-1)^i}{i!}$	Number of permutations of the first h natural numbers, such that none of them occupies the position indicated by its value
μ	$\min\{h, k-h\}$	